

Exploring inclusiveness in the Engineering student experience at UoA

In this questionnaire, you will spend about 15 minutes thinking about your experiences in the Faculty of Engineering over the last year, how you see yourself as an Engineering student in general, and how you think about your future career. Please be completely honest about what you think, there are no right or wrong answers. All questions are optional and may be skipped. Participation in this research is entirely voluntary, and you may leave the online questionnaire at any point prior to submission without any responses being recorded. **Once you have submitted your responses, we will not be able to remove them from the dataset as they are anonymous.** Sometimes questionnaires such as this one may provoke strong emotions in respondents, and if this occurs for you, we encourage you to seek support from any of the counseling services available through the website provided in the Participant Information Sheet.

Approved by the University of Auckland Human Participants Ethics Committee on 16/6/2021 for three years. Reference Number UAHPEC22566.

What year of study are you currently in? (choose one)

- Part 1
 - Part 2
 - Part 3
 - Part 4
-

Display This Question:

If Year of study = Part 1

Which specialisation do you intend to study in Part 2? (Choose one)

- Biomedical Engineering
 - Chemical and Materials Engineering
 - Civil Engineering
 - Computer Systems Engineering
 - Electrical and Electronic Engineering
 - Engineering Science
 - Mechanical Engineering
 - Mechatronics Engineering
 - Software Engineering
 - Structural Engineering
 - Have not decided yet
-

Display This Question:

If Year of study != Part 1

What is your current specialisation? (Choose one)

- Biomedical Engineering
 - Chemical and Materials Engineering
 - Civil Engineering
 - Computer Systems Engineering
 - Electrical and Electronic Engineering
 - Engineering Science
 - Mechanical Engineering
 - Mechatronics Engineering
 - Software Engineering
 - Structural Engineering
-

Display This Question:

If Year of study != Part 1

What was your first choice of specialisation? (Choose one)

- Biomedical Engineering
 - Chemical and Materials Engineering
 - Civil Engineering
 - Computer Systems Engineering
 - Electrical and Electronic Engineering
 - Engineering Science
 - Mechanical Engineering
 - Mechatronics Engineering
 - Software Engineering
 - Structural Engineering
-

Display This Question:

If Year of study != Part 1

When did you decide on your current choice of specialisation? (Choose one)

- Before starting my Engineering degree
- During Part 1 of my Engineering degree
- Changed my mind after starting in a different specialisation

Consider the courses/papers you are taking this year (including all associated activities such as lectures, labs, fieldwork), and the department that your specialisation or courses sit within. Select the option that most closely matches how much you agree with each of the following statements.

	Strongly disagree	Somewhat disagree	Neutral	Somewhat agree	Strongly agree	I don't know
People in my courses/papers accept me.	<input type="radio"/>					
Other students understand more than I do about what is going on in my courses/papers.	<input type="radio"/>					
I fit in well with others in my courses/papers.	<input type="radio"/>					
I get along well with people in my courses/papers.	<input type="radio"/>					
I have a lot in common with people in my courses/papers.	<input type="radio"/>					
I do not feel like I am part of the team during group assignments.	<input type="radio"/>					
I think my lecturers treat me with respect.	<input type="radio"/>					
I feel like an outsider in [my specialisation / the Faculty of Engineering].	<input type="radio"/>					
I think in the same way as other people who do well in [my specialisation / the Faculty of Engineering].	<input type="radio"/>					
I feel alienated from other students in [my specialisation / the Faculty of Engineering].	<input type="radio"/>					
I think I am similar to the kind of people who succeed in [my specialisation / the Faculty of Engineering].	<input type="radio"/>					

I think I belong in [my specialisation / the Faculty of Engineering].

I actively participate in at least one student group/society in the Faculty of Engineering.

I have friends in the Faculty of Engineering.

I think I can be myself around my friends in the Faculty of Engineering.

Please add anything else you would like to share about your experiences in relation to the statements above.

Now think about how you are feeling about your studies this year. Select the option that most closely matches how much you agree with each of the following statements:

	Strongly disagree	Somewhat disagree	Neutral	Somewhat agree	Strongly agree	I don't know
I enjoy studying Engineering.	<input type="radio"/>					
I am satisfied with my decision to study engineering.	<input type="radio"/>					
<i>Display This Choice:</i>						
<i>If Year of study != Part 1</i>						
I am satisfied with my decision to study my chosen specialisation.	<input type="radio"/>					
I often think about leaving Engineering.	<input type="radio"/>					
I would recommend studying Engineering to others.	<input type="radio"/>					
I will be able to achieve most of the goals that I have set for myself.	<input type="radio"/>					
When facing difficult tasks, I am certain that I will accomplish them.	<input type="radio"/>					
In general, I think that I can obtain outcomes that are important to me.	<input type="radio"/>					
I believe I can succeed at most any endeavor to which I set my mind.	<input type="radio"/>					
I will be able to successfully overcome many challenges.	<input type="radio"/>					
I am confident that I can perform effectively on many different tasks.	<input type="radio"/>					

Compared to other people, I can do most tasks very well.

Even when things are tough, I can perform quite well.

I feel an overall sense of accomplishment in my studies

Please add anything else you would like to share about your experiences in relation to the statements above.

Thinking ahead to when you have finished your degree, select the option that most closely matches how much you agree with each of the following statements:

	Strongly disagree	Somewhat disagree	Neutral	Somewhat agree	Strongly agree	I don't know
I have a good chance of getting a job when I graduate	<input type="radio"/>					
I will be well paid as an engineer	<input type="radio"/>					
I think I know what an engineer does at work	<input type="radio"/>					
I will be respected by others	<input type="radio"/>					
I will probably not end up unemployed as an engineer	<input type="radio"/>					
I am interested in the work I would be doing, and I will enjoy doing it	<input type="radio"/>					
I will have a lot of spare time	<input type="radio"/>					
I can have a good career	<input type="radio"/>					
I think I will still be employed in engineering 10 years from now	<input type="radio"/>					
I will have supportive colleagues in this profession	<input type="radio"/>					
I will have enough time to take care of my family	<input type="radio"/>					
I think the skills I learn in Engineering will be transferable to jobs other fields	<input type="radio"/>					
If I had to do it over again, I would still choose to study engineering	<input type="radio"/>					

Please add anything else you would like to share about your experiences in relation to the statements above.

In this section we are asking you to provide demographic information. We are gathering this data because we are exploring how welcome and included students feel in relation to their sense of identity. All questions are optional, so please answer as honestly as you can, and feel free to choose not to disclose this information if you prefer.

Please choose the option that applies to you:

- I am a domestic student
- I am an international student
- I prefer not to disclose

Which ethnicity do you identify with? (you can choose multiple)

- NZ Māori
- Samoan
- Cook Islands Māori
- Tongan
- Niuean
- Fijian
- Tokelauan
- Japanese
- Korean
- Chinese
- Indian
- Middle Eastern
- Latin American
- African

- NZ European
 - Other European
 - Prefer not to disclose
 - Prefer to self-describe
-

What gender do you identify with? (you can choose multiple)

- Woman
 - Man
 - Non-binary
 - Prefer not to disclose
 - Prefer to self-describe
-

What sexual orientation do you identify with? (you can choose multiple)

- Straight or heterosexual
 - Gay or lesbian
 - Bisexual
 - Don't know
 - Prefer not to disclose
 - Prefer to self-describe
-

Do you have difficulties with your studies because of any physical or mental impairments? (A physical or mental impairment is defined as something that has a substantial and long-term impact on your ability to carry out day-to-day activities. It could be caused by accident, trauma, genetics, or disease. It may be temporary or permanent, total or partial, lifelong or acquired, visible or invisible.)

- Yes
- No
- Prefer not to disclose

*Display This Question:
If Impairment = Yes*

Please add more details on your physical or mental impairment if you wish:
